

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: THERENCE NWANA****FIRST NAME: DINGANA****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (MS Word on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. The art of academic essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-9)
2. The structure/format of academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 10-14)
3. American and British English punctuations and language variants (EUCLID 2021, 15-32)
4. Plagiarism, their implications, and how to avoid them (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

After reading the study material for ACA-401, I realized the content aims to improve academic communication. I appreciate the authors' opinion on how academic essays should be planned, developed, and written. I have also known the differences between British and American English and that using just one style at a time is rational enough. Some key writing skills, styles, and punctuation have also been digested. I have always copied documents from the web or textbooks, modified them, and used little did I know I was practicing plagiarism. Through this lecture note, I have assimilated a lot about writing properly and acknowledging people's knowledge by citing their work when used. This lecture has also prepared me for the task ahead by explaining how major and response papers should be written.

I spent an unusually long period studying this material and also exploring the platform and how to maneuver it. I am now ready to engage in the other study periods with more determination and confidence.

In this response paper, I have written on the art of academic essay writing, the structure and format of an academic essay, and the use of the American or the British

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English language styles in academic writing and, avoiding plagiarism by citing references to acknowledge original authors.

2) THE ART OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

Of the different types of essays that exist, I have greatly acquainted myself with the methodic approach to academic essays, which is employed in writing research, reporting fieldwork, student reports, etc. (“Cleenewerck & Gulma” 2021, 7). I have understood the steps in writing academic essays and that these steps are not rigid but that every academic essay should at least follow the following steps: starting early, analyzing the task, drafting a plan, and then writing the easy proper (“Cleenewerck & Gulma” 2021, 7).

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3) THE STRUCTURE/FORMAT OF ACADEMIC ESSAYS

I mastered in ACA401 that academic essays have a specific structure comprising an introduction, a body, and a conclusion (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 10-11). The introduction conveys materials from general to more specific concepts and is usually brief and mentions main ideas. The body comprises paragraphs, each contributing a building block in the argument. The conclusion opens the ideas and moves from specific to broader concepts.

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I have also become skilled with some key tips for writing an essay which entail: starting early, writing in parts, writing the introduction and conclusion only after the body of the essay has been written, doing a thorough revision of the first draft, and making corrections, keeping the essay away, and revisiting it a few days later to proofread and make corrections, especially on grammar and punctuation (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 11).

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4) AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH PUNCTUATIONS AND LANGUAGE VARIANTS

In ACA401, I also revisited some key notions of punctuations, emphasizing apostrophes, brackets, angle brackets, bullet points, colons, semicolons, commas, and quotation marks (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 16-23). And as a rule of thumb, I should avoid using too many punctuation marks and endeavor to make sense of the sentence.

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I understood that there are many forms of the English language, but the two most common are American and British English. American English is more dominant due to its worldwide economic, political, technological, and cultural influence. American and British English have many things in common. Still, there are many differences in terms of pronunciations of words with the exact spellings, words spelled differently but pronounced the same, differences in syntax, grammar, punctuation, and words usages and

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the use of different words or phrases to refer to the same thing or concept(Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 25-32).

5) PLAGIARISM, THEIR IMPLICATIONS, AND HOW TO AVOID THEM

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I agree with the author of the course park of this moduel that plagiarism is a writing misconduct in which the writer takes information from another author without acknowledging the author and therefore presenting the idea like his. this is a very big academic mischief that can ruin the career of the culprit(Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 34).

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To avoid plagiarism, the works of others must be cited and referenced or put in quotation marks which may look too clumsy if too many or rewritten in my own words(paraphrasing) that look very different from how the original author wrote it and again this should be cited and referenced(Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 35-36).

6) STYLE GUIDES

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Although the use of punctuation and correct grammar in the English language is well well-known and specified, style is much more than the accurate use of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary.

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Different bodies have adopted various styles to make their writings look unique, for example, technical writing, business writing, journalism, etc. the different styles used are based on specifications on; sentence lengths, font size, styles, spellings(whether UK or US), the use of abbreviations, use of symbols, etc. (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 41-42).

7) CONCLUSION

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Rules and styles govern academic essay writing; therefore, every student must acquaint themselves with the required structure and practice the art of academic essay writing. While adopting these structures and styles, the student must use the correct punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary while taking special precautions to avoid plagiarism and implementing the appropriate writing style as stipulated in the context of the writing, and adopting the suitable variant of the English language

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REFERENCES

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

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Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.